

SITE GPR	YEAR 2012	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min Max:	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1507 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropoc	Gabii I	
In cross-section? ☐ Yes ☒ No		In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☒ No		Photos: ☒ Yes ☐ No #: 2718-19	Photo Model: ☐ Yes ☒ No #:		
DEFINITION Circular stone vessel 2				Covered by ☐ SU:	Fills ☐ SU:	Filled by ☐ SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☒ Color ☐ Composition ☐ Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS ☐ Accumulation ☐ Construction ☐ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☐ Collapse ☒ Intentional deposition				
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are				SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% ☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive			
Anthropic		Geological		Organic			
☐ Pottery ☐ Tiles ☐ Amphorae ☐ Dolia ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Mortar ☐ Coins ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Glass		☐ Nails ☐ Marble ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Other (specify)		☐ Tufo (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)		☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft
Compaction		Color					
☐ Black ☐ Gray ☐ Light Gray ☐ Yellow ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)		☐ Brown ☐ Light Brown ☐ White ☐ Red ☐ Other (specify)					

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)				Depth: ☒ Original ☐ Not Original	
Northern Limit	☒ Original	☐ Not Original	☐ Excavation Limit		
Southern Limit	☒ Original	☐ Not Original	☐ Excavation Limit		
Western Limit	☒ Original	☐ Not Original	☐ Excavation Limit		
Eastern Limit	☒ Original	☐ Not Original	☐ Excavation Limit		

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE		Is bound to (only for masonry):	
Is equal to:		Abuts:	
Is abutted by:		Covers:	
Is covered by: SU 0		Cuts:	
Is cut by:		Fills:	

OBSERVATIONS
Vessel was spotted at the last day of GPP '11-season and stays in situ

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: southernmost limit of area B, central position
Shape: Circular

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction, visible inclusions):
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

orange tufo
vessel (one piece)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type:

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

tufo vessel

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

conical, almost bucket-shaped stone vessel,
one piece, maybe belonging to wine or oil
press equipments.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by

CHH

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